

Quality Clinical Supervision and Teachers' Instructional Delivery in Public Secondary Schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study focused on quality clinical supervision and teachers' instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. Two research questions and two hypotheses were employed in the study. The target population was 160 principals and vice-principals in 80 schools in the area which was purposively used as the sample size. Data were obtained through a researcher-developed instrument tagged "Quality Clinical Supervision and Teachers' Instructional Delivery Questionnaire (QCSTIDQ)". The validated questionnaire with 36 items passed through split-half reliability using Spearman Brown's coefficient which yielded 0.67-0.77. Data obtained were coded and transferred to a statistical package for social science (SPSS) for analysis using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis. The hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The results of the analysis showed a significant relationship between quality clinical supervision and teachers' instructional delivery. It was recommended among others that classroom observation should be well planned and encouraged in our secondary school system, clinical supervision cycle should be followed systematically to promote instructional delivery and encourage professional development in the teachers.

Keywords: Analysis, classroom observation, clinical supervision, supervision, teachers' instructional delivery

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Introduction

Every teacher in the secondary schools deems to develop a skill that brings about proficiency in instructional delivery leading to effective students' learning outcomes. Teachers require appropriate knowledge, materials, support and leadership that promote quality instruction in the classroom setting. This is critical because the obtainment of any school goal is dependent upon the quality of instruction delivered by the academic staff in any educational institution of learning. Researchers have repeatedly emphasized teachers' instructional effectiveness as the

most important factor that triggers students' learning and quality control in the school. Fischer (2012) buttressed the fact that the quality of students' learning is related to the quality of classroom instructions. Teachers in secondary schools are always faced with the challenge of providing high-quality instruction to the clientele (the students). Also, Uko (2014) averred that except appropriate standards are maintained in the school system, the predetermined goals of education cannot be maintained.

It is worrisome and pricking that most teachers in secondary schools are ineffective in instructional delivery and lack appropriate knowledge in different disciplines to feed the students. A vast majority lack questioning skills, classroom management techniques, as well as skills of writing notes of lessons. To support this, Shamaki (2011) observed that concerned people have come out to lament teachers' ineffectiveness educational system in society. This directs the cursor to the fact that there is a problem of low educational quality in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. These may be traceable to supervisory ineffective and the inability of the principals to effectively implement clinical supervision in our secondary school system. Babalola and Ayemi (2009) posited that sustainable development in teaching standards and learning behaviours is best assured when the classroom environment is well monitored and supervised. Clinical supervision is a systematic and organized strategy for improving teachers' instruction in the classroom. It involves a planned one-on-one meeting or encounter between the clinical supervisor and the teacher on the events that take place in the classroom. This approach to supervision is operated in a step-wise manner including observation conferences, classroom observation and supervision analysis.

Secondary school teachers' effectiveness and skill development vis-à-vis instructional delivery are dependent upon the instructional supports and leadership provided by the school administrators. Such supports revolve around clinical supervision, good communication, supply of instructional materials and exposure to new knowledge. Doubtlessly, despite government efforts in promoting teachers' professional development and prompt payment of salaries, most teachers still have a deficiency in instructional delivery, low productivity, and lack of job satisfaction. Some lack knowledge of the subject matter, while others lack pedagogical skills in the classroom during instructional delivery. More so, most teachers lack appropriate skills in writing notes of lessons and are ineffective in managing their classes. These problems are attributed to some principal's lack of proficiency in carrying out clinical supervision which is an innovative approach as well and the "will and zeal" of supervising instruction. The result of such anomalies is poor learning outcomes. These problems necessitated the study to examine the relationship between quality clinical supervision and teachers' instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State – Nigeria.

Literature review

Clinical supervision is a systematic and planned process of directing coordinating and observation of teachers in instructional activities that take place in the classroom for improvement. Okon (2016) observed that clinical supervision is necessary to maintain a

standard and ensure that students are exposed to intensive instruction. According to Akpa (2002), clinical supervision takes account of teachers' behaviours and teaching in supportive, analytical and non-evaluative content. Clinical supervision has its origin from the medical provision, where the principal is likened to the expert surgeon, the teacher as an inexperienced surgeon, the students as the patients while the classroom serves as the "clinic" where instructional problems are diagnosed and treated. In considering the critical role of clinical supervision, Wijaya (2013) buttressed the fact that the principal has to use the clinical cycle to improve the teachers' skills in preparing lesson notes, lesson presentations, and also give feedback to the teachers on the events that take place in the classroom.

Classroom observation is the mainstay and the pivot in the clinical process and involves the face-to-face encounter in the classroom between the principal and the supervisee on the particular events (instruction) that takes place in the classroom. Okon (2016) averred that classroom observation is strictly non-judgmental but promotes teaching skills, teachers' practices and consequently enhances learning outcomes. It, therefore, follows that, after the classroom visit or observation, the principal analyzes the activities that hitherto took place in the classroom by providing feedback to the teachers for further improvement. The supervisor observes the teacher in the classroom using the conceptual framework articulated during the pre-observation conference. Classroom observation is strictly non-judgmental but promotes teaching skills, teachers' practice and consequently enhances learning outcomes. Sule (2010) carried out a study on the relationship between classroom visitation and teachers' job performance. The results showed that there was a significant relationship between classroom observation and teachers' job performance. A study was also conducted by Aniah (2005) on classroom observation and teachers' productivity using 500 teachers. The result revealed a significant relationship between classroom visitation/observation and teachers' productivity. Fischer (2012) carried out a study on classroom observation, teacher evaluation and classroom performance. The result showed that classroom observation information and other data as well as how to translate results of observation encourage teachers to improve instruction.

Another study was conducted by Cheshier (2015) on the impact of classroom observation on fourth-grade mathematics teachers at Collieville elementary schools. This pilot programme was done in six Tennessee school districts. The findings revealed that the practice of senior-teacher or principal observing teachers is part of teacher excellence programmes. Considerably, a classroom observation is an important tool for teachers' effectiveness. Hopkins and Moore (2006) posited that supervision analysis done by the superior involves the analysis of classroom data and the development of appropriate strategies that would lead to an improvement in the instructional process. Several attempts have been made by scholars to investigate the relationship between supervision analysis and teacher's instructional role performance. Okorji and Ogbo (2013) carried out a study on the effect of modified clinical supervision on teachers' instructional performance using 820 teachers. The result revealed that Cogan's supervision approach proved more effective than the traditional approach with the mean score of 80.35 and 59.9 respectively. This means that supervision analysis proves to be effective in improving the instructional performance of teachers. Fischer (2012) averred that, by skillfully analyzing performance and appropriate data, administrators can provide

meaningful feedback and direction to teachers that can have a profound effect on the learning that occurs in each classroom.

A similar study was conducted by Kiprighetich and Kirui (2013) on the use of clinical cycle on teachers' trainees in Physical Education in Rift-Valley Zone in Kenya. The findings of the study showed that there was a significant relationship between supervision and analysis and teachers' performance. A study was undertaken by Oyewole and Alonge (2013) on principals' supervisory roles and teachers' motivation to work. This implies that supervision analysis done by the principal is an important tool that motivates teachers to work effectively. Goldammer in Marzono, Frontier and Livingstone (2011) buttressed the fact that the purpose of analysis in clinical supervision is to analyze teachers' professional behaviours. Duyar, Ras and Pearson (2015) studied analysis of teachers' task and extra-role performance. The findings revealed a positive relationship between analysis of teachers' tasks and extra-role performance. In consonance with this, Pajak (2001) remarked that feedbacks given during analysis-of-analysis are likely to continue to play important role in the ongoing quest to further the professional growth of the beginning and experienced teachers.

Brennen (2011) in a case study of clinical supervision with the Biology/Integrated Science teachers stated that post-conference analysis was employed to assess the clinical supervision process to understand whether or not the teacher understands and agrees with the follow-up and improvement target. Schmoker (2007) declared that classroom data well analyzed can help the teacher improve teaching that has an impact on students' learning. Range (2013) averred that effective principals routinely visit teachers' classrooms and provide formative and corrective feedback through analysis of data collected during the supervision process. Hopkins and Moore (2006) posited that, in post-observation analysis, the supervisor (principal) may invite another superior for an examination of the effectiveness of the clinical process which leads to teachers' effectiveness. According to Jerald (2012), accurate feedback based on observation instruments can be a powerful resource for improving teaching and learning.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between classroom observation and teachers' instructional delivery in secondary schools.
2. There is no significant relationship between supervision analysis and teachers' instructional delivery in secondary schools.

Methods

This study was carried in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. Two research questions and two hypotheses were employed in the study. The target population was 160 principals and vice-principals in 80 schools in the area which was purposively used as sample size. Data was

obtained through a researcher-develop instrument tagged “Quality Clinical Supervision and Teachers’ Instructional Delivery Questionnaire (QCSTIDQ)”. The validated questionnaire was divided into three sections (A, B, and C). Section A consisted of demographic variables while B and C contain 36 items (18 each). The questionnaire passed through split-half reliability using Spearman’s Brown Co-efficient which yielded .67–.77. Data were collected through questionnaire administration and the data were coded and transferred to statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) for analysis using Pearson’s Products Moment Correlation Coefficient. The hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between classroom observation and teachers’ instructional delivery in secondary schools.

Table 1: Pearson's product-moment correlation analysis of the relationship between classroom observation and teachers’ instructional delivery in secondary schools.

Variables	X	SD	ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣXY	rXY	Sig.
			ΣY	ΣY^2			
Classroom observation	22.14	1.85	3,542	78,996	76,430	0.476*	.000
Teachers’ instructional Delivery	21.52	1.76	3,441	74,487			

- $P < .05$, $df = 158$, critical $r = 159$

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between supervision analysis and teachers’ instructional delivery in secondary schools.

Table 2: Pearson's product-moment correlation analysis of the relationship between supervision analysis and teachers’ instructional delivery in secondary schools.

Variables	X	SD	ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣXY	rXY	Sig.
			ΣY	ΣY^2			
Supervision analysis	21.07	2.14	3,371	71,751	72,746	0.419*	.000
Teachers’ instructional Delivery	21.52	1.76	3,441	74,487			

- $P < .05$, $df = 158$, critical $r = 159$

Discussion of findings

The result of hypothesis one as presented in Table 1 revealed that there is a significant relationship between classroom observation and teachers' instructional delivery in secondary schools. This result necessitated the rejection of the null hypothesis and its restatement. This implies that the more effective classroom observation the better the teachers' instructional delivery. This was in line with Sule (2010) who found that there was a significant relationship between classroom observation and teachers' relationship exists between classroom visitation/observation and teachers' productivity. Also, Fischer (2012) observed that classroom observation and other data as well as how to translate results of observation encourage teachers to improve instruction. This finding was also in consonance with Cheshier (2015) who discover that the practice of senior teachers observing teachers is part of teacher excellence programmes. Considerably, observation is important for teachers' effectiveness in the world of school.

The result of hypothesis two as presented in table 2 reveals that there is a significant relationship between supervision analysis and teachers' instructional delivery in secondary school. The result necessitated the rejection of the null hypothesis and the restatement of the alternative hypothesis. This was inconsonant with Hopkins and Moore (2006) who posited that supervision analysis done by the supervisors involves analysis of classroom data and development of appropriate strategies that would lead to an improvement in the instructional process. Okorji and Ogbo (2013) also discovered that Cogan's supervision approach proved to be more effective than the traditional approach. This means that supervision analysis is critical for improving the instructional performance of teachers. Fischer (2012) averred that, by skillfully analyzing performance and appropriate data, administrators can provide meaningful feedback and directions to teachers that can have profound effects on the learning that takes place in the classroom. Also, Kiprighetich and Kirui (2013) discovered a significant relationship between supervision analysis and teachers' performance. In line with this, Oyewole and Alonge (2013) found that a significant relationship exists between principals' supervisory rule and teachers' motivation to work. This finding implies that supervision analysis carried by a senior teacher is an important tool for motivating teachers.

Goldhammar in Marzono, Frontier and Livingstone (2011) buttressed the fact that the purpose of analysis in clinical supervision is to analyse teachers' professional behaviour. Duyar, Ras and Pearson (2015) observed that there is a positive relationship between analysis of teachers' tasks and extra-role performance. In consonance with this, Pajak (2001) remarked that feedbacks given during analysis are likely to continue to play important role in the professional growth of the beginning of and experienced teachers. Brennen (2011) stated that post-conference analysis was employed to assess the clinical supervision process and understand whether or not the teacher understands and agrees with the follow-up improvement target. To affirm this, Schmoker (2007) averred that effective principals routinely visit teachers' classrooms and provide formative and corrective feedback through analysis of data collected during the supervision process. Hopkins and Moore (2006) posited that post-observation analysis involves the invitation of another supervisor for the examination of the effectiveness

of the clinical process leading to teachers' effectiveness. Also, Jerald (2012) observed that accurate feedback based on observation instruments can be a powerful resource for improving teaching and learning.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, it was concluded that quality clinical supervision variables such as classroom observation and supervision analysis have a positive relationship with teachers' instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made

1. Classroom observation should be well planned and encouraged in our public secondary school system.
2. After the classroom, visitation/observation supervision analysis should be carried out to provide meaningful feedback on the events that took place in the classroom.
3. The clinical supervision cycle should be followed systematically to promote classroom effectiveness and professional development in the teachers.

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